

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF EMPATHIC RELATIONSHIPS IN STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The formation of empathic attitude is manifested in the unity of interpersonal perception, emotional experience and communication processes and is considered a factor ensuring cooperation, mutual understanding and social adaptation in educational activities. The development of empathy in students is associated with the educational environment, didactic tools and the communicative activity of the individual, and is carried out through the combination of emotional-perceptive and cognitive processes.

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The formation of empathic attitude in students is one of the most important socio-psychological directions of the modern educational process. Empathy is manifested in the educational process as a stable factor of cooperation between students, the content of teacher-student relations, communicative culture, personal mutual understanding and professional formation. Empathy is the ability of a person to understand the state of another person, accept their emotional experiences and respond appropriately to them. Empathy in the educational process is important not only as an educational tool, but also as a professional competence. Because future specialists, especially teachers, in their future activities will work with different social groups, which requires communicative cooperation. According to the research of Omonova M., empathetic relationships are a component of deontological training and serve to form subject-subject relationships in the educational process, which is one of the necessary conditions for personal and professional achievements.

The content of empathy is explained differently in the psychological literature. Emotional empathy is the ability of a person to perceive the emotions of others as an internal experience, while cognitive empathy is explained by the logical analysis of the situation and the determination of an appropriate strategy of influence on it. The combination of these two processes helps to consciously organize a person's attitude towards others. In this, factors such

as the student's ability to manage his emotions, awareness of his own identity, social experience, and openness to communication are important. The process of identification plays a special role in the formation of empathy, because when a student puts himself in the place of others, he better understands their situation and achieves constructive thinking. In addition to the psychological preparation of the individual, pedagogical conditions are also necessary for the development of empathy in the educational process. First of all, the pedagogical environment should be organized in such a way that cooperation, openness, mutual respect, readiness for communication and opportunities for exchange of ideas are ensured between the teacher and the student. Omonova indicates dialogical communication as an important pedagogical mechanism in the formation of empathy and evaluates it as an emotional-intellectual stimulant, since this communication activates both the student's thinking process and emotional perception. Deontological culture also plays an important role in the development of empathy. Professional ethical standards, moral responsibility, fulfillment of duty to society, adherence to the rules of cultural communication - all this constitutes the moral foundation of empathy. Omonova's scientific work shows three functions of the deontological approach: regulative (regulating behavior), image (creating a positive professional image), and translational (transmitting cultural values to generations). This means that empathy should be considered not only as an individual virtue, but also as a professional skill that ensures social stability and cooperation in society. There are also methods that help develop empathy.

Identification is the student's putting himself in another's place, cognitive interpretation is the interpretation and explanation of the content of the situation, summarization is the generalization of the content of the conversation, and encouragement serves to support the student. These methods enhance the process of social understanding in the student's mind, instill trust, and form a culture of active listening. There are also factors that hinder the development of empathy. These include an authoritarian pedagogical approach, artificial competition between students, lack of emotional support, and the fact that the educational process is based only on assessment and control. Such factors can cause coldness, alienation, and mutual distrust in students. Therefore, the principle of cooperation in education is important. The teacher himself should be an example of empathetic relationships. Because the student is often influenced by the teacher's character, communication style, speech culture, and emotional attitude. The teacher's desire to understand the student, his attentiveness to him, and his willingness to help have a direct positive impact on the formation of empathy. Thus, the formation of empathy in students is inextricably linked with psychological preparation, communication culture, pedagogical environment, person-oriented approach, and deontological values. Empathy is manifested not as a human quality of a person, but as an integral part of the educational process, a key component of professional formation. An empathetic student will develop in the future as a conscious, responsible, and tolerant person who can work effectively with others, ensure social stability in society..

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